

Towards Offshore Hydrogen Platform in Tunisia: The Key-Steps

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Among serious investments that enhance economic growth in Tunisia is developing alternative and renewable energy resources such as sustainable workflow for Hydrogen production.

Three majors steps are controlled to overcome efficient capacity :

- * Having good quality water input
- * Assembling upscaled water electrolysis
- * Compressed Hydrogen to transfer or storage

Many systems of water treatment are existing based on desalination concepts or osmosis and can be used or depicted from several previous experiences [1-3].

Brines revalorization is also an important task to keep reasonable circular economy and to avoid unwanted oversalted areas [4-7].

Image Courtesy: Comprehensive illustration of Tunisian Hydrogen Platform

Water electrolysis devices are actually being democratized to reach the standards of secure industrial applications. Several devices are available and covered in the global market from classic Alkaline Stack up to the Proton Exchange Membrane PEM cell. Other modules are also considered like the Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOEC) or the Alkaline Anion Exchange Membrane AEM cell. All of them depends on the membrane type, intercalated anion, rate of hydrogen or its pressure output and the equivalent solar/wind input power needed [8-11].

Chemical equation

The last important step is the end-product refinement from purification/compression to obtain high pressure gaseous hydrogen H₂ up to the storage facilities [12-17] or direct pipeline transfer [18].

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